

Additional file 2

Figure S2. Calibration of the near-linear range of the various substrate hydrolyses. Increased cellulosome dosages were applied on (A) 7% microcrystalline cellulose (MCC), (B) 5% alkaline-pretreated switch grass [aISG], (C) 5% alkaline-pretreated corn stover [aICS] and (D) 5% dilute acid-pretreated corn stover [acCS], and the samples were incubated overnight at 70°C. Released sugar concentrations were measured by dinitrosalicylic acid (DNS) method, as previously described [1]. All assays were performed with the addition of 0.33 mg/ml equivalent of *Thermoanaerobacter brockii* β -glucosidase (CglT) in order to prevent feedback inhibition. Enzyme loadings of 20, 50, 3 and 50 µg/ml for MCC, aISG, aICS and acCS hydrolysis assays, respectively, were chosen for activity measurements (Black arrows).

References

1. Miller GL. Use of dinitrosalicylic acid reagent for determination of reducing sugar. *Anal Biochem.* 1959;31:426–428.